

Report on Second Round of Benchmarks Deliverable D3.8

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes the second round of benchmarks conducted under the NEWA validation strategy. This report is the second of a series of three annual reports on NEWA benchmarks.

The **first round** of microscale benchmarks was directed to developing microscale models that can be driven with mesoscale input forcing, include thermal stratification of the atmospheric boundary layer and high resolution digital models of heterogeneous forest canopy characteristics based on aerial lidar-scan data. These fundamental implementations were developed around the GABLS3 diurnal-cycle and Ryningsnäs forest canopy benchmarks, both in flat terrain conditions. By model intercomparison, NEWA modelers found reasonably good consistency in the simulation of these cases, establishing common understanding of the modeling capabilities of the group before attempting more complex simulation challenges in connection to the NEWA experiments.

The first release of the NEWA model chain is produced based on this first round of benchmarks. CFDWind3 is published open-access to engage with early adopters that can help testing and eventually developing new functionalities alongside the NEWA validation plans.

The **second round** of benchmarks has been focused on the following objectives:

- Validation of flow models from flat to **hilly forested terrain**: Experimental data from the Rödeser Berg and Hornamossen experiments add terrain complexity to the baseline settings used in GABLS3 and Ryningsnäs. Following the Ryningsnäs approach, a blind test addressing steady-state models was organized around the Rödeser Berg forested hill benchmark. On the other hand, Hornamossen followed the GABLS3 approach to challenge transient models in the simulation of diurnal cycles on an undulated forested landscape.
- Assessment of **annual wind conditions** relevant for wind resource assessment and site suitability. The “NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge for Wind Resource Assessment” addresses the evaluation of a hierarchy of methodologies that incorporate mesoscale-to-microscale downscaling to understand the added-value compared to traditional approaches for site assessment that rely only on microscale modeling. This challenge is divided in two phases: the first one in flat terrain and the second one in complex terrain conditions. This report summarizes results for the first phase based on Cabauw and Fino1 sites in onshore and offshore conditions.
- Development of an **open-science benchmarking** approach: the benchmarking process established in GABLS3 is rolled out in the next benchmarks to promote a more traceable model evaluation based on sharing of simulation data and evaluation scripts.

This report presents benchmark guides for Rödeser Berg, Hornamossen and the NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge and initial results published for the first phase of the Challenge.

The third round of benchmarks will exploit experimental data in complex terrain in terms of flow cases targeting the validation of specific modeling features, as well as case studies that integrate these models in wind resource assessment methodologies to assess the impact of those features in terms of relevant quantities of interest for the wind industry (annual energy prediction, site assessment characteristics, mean profiles, etc).

Introduction

The NEWA validation strategy is covered in [1] and the first round of benchmarks in [2]. NEWA experimental data and benchmarking activities are leveraged to the international community under the umbrella of the IEA-Wind Task 31 *Wakebench*. This allows engaging with a wider range of researchers and models and supports the integration of NEWA model evaluation procedures in Task 31 Model Evaluation Protocol [3].

The verification and validation (V&V) framework established in Task 31 is based on the one developed at Sandia National Laboratories [4] which, itself, follows existing methodologies developed by various American organizations including the American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) [5] and the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) [6]. The framework is briefly introduced here to explain how NEWA contributes to fill the building blocks for the validation of models for the assessment of wind conditions.

1. NEWA Validation Building Blocks for Wind Conditions

1.1. The Wakebench V&V Framework

The segmented pyramid of Figure 1 is used in the second version of the *Wakebench* Model Evaluation Protocol [3] to represent the relationships between different building blocks of the validation framework in terms of atmospheric and wind power system scales. A hierarchy of increasing flow complexity is established as higher levels of coupling between relevant physical phenomena are added towards a full system validation. In practice, full system validation is not possible though because this would require experiments in all operational conditions. Instead, the evaluation process aims at improving model credibility to mitigate uncertainties in the prediction of relevant quantities for the application of interest.

A V&V framework facilitates discussions between the scientific community and industry to identify the knowledge gaps (experiments, model development and validation) that should be addressed with higher priority to improve the predictive capacity of models. Consensus on relevant phenomena for wind farm models in view of their validation track record is formulated in a Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) which is utilized as a planning tool to guide the validation strategy [1].

Figure 1: System scales and phenomena of interest for "wind" (right, dark grey hierarchy) and "wake" conditions (left, light grey hierarchy) [7].

1.2. NEWA Validation Building Blocks for Wind Conditions

The coupling of mesoscale and microscale models implies drastic changes in the implementation of microscale models that can benefit from more realistic transient boundary conditions, as opposed to using steady-state canonical inflow conditions. However, general adoption by industry requires a cost-benefit justification by comparing with current engineering models. The NEWA "Meso-Micro Challenge" is addressing this opportunity based on a suite of validation datasets derived from experiments in a range of site and wind climate conditions, from homogeneous (Cabauw, Fino1) to heterogeneous flows due to terrain and vegetation changes (Ryningsnäs, Rödeser Berg, Hornamossen, Perdiago and Alaiz) [8].

Figure 2 expands the hierarchy of building blocks of Figure 1 for the validation of wind-conditions models and highlights the complementarities of NEWA experiments. At the top of the pyramid, the "NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge" addresses full-system validation towards the quantification of the accuracy and validity range of wind resource assessment methodologies. These methodologies typically integrate the long-term wind climate with site effects through a dynamical-statistical downscaling process. The underlying flow models of these methodologies improve their predictive capacity by incorporating relevant physical phenomena which are systematically validated at increasing levels complexity as illustrated in the sidelines of the diagram.

Figure 2: Building-block hierarchy for the validation of wind-conditions models and associated NEWA experiments addressing relevant phenomena of interest.

For instance, at the lowest tier, models will try to comply with Monin-Obukhov Similarity Theory (MOST) to deal with stability-dependent wind conditions in the surface-layer under horizontally homogeneous conditions, a widely used surface boundary condition for atmospheric boundary layers. Beyond the surface layer, models would incorporate the Coriolis force and free-atmosphere conditions (capping inversion, geostrophic wind) to simulate an idealized ABL. Then, adding transient surface conditions and large-scale forcing (also called tendencies) allows simulating a realistic ABL along, for instance, a typical diurnal cycle like in the GABLS3 case [9]. Adding horizontal heterogeneity due to roughness, vegetation and elevation changes comes next with increasing complexity targeting relevant phenomena like: drastic changes of surface roughness and heat flux conditions in coastal transitions, flow above forest canopies, flow above hills from gentle to steep slopes leading to flow separation, interaction between the thermally stratified ABL and terrain at different characteristic configurations from isolated hills, hill-hill interaction, and with larger obstacles. Some of these microscale effects can be systematically studied in the controlled environment of a wind tunnel, by parametric testing of idealized topographic configurations. Different flow regimes shall be studied based on similarity parameters like the Froude number, which can explain the formation of terrain-induced effects like the blockage of the flow in front of topographic obstacles and the generation of lee (gravity) waves in stable conditions [10]. Microscale site

effects in field conditions are always subject to large-scale weather phenomena that can trigger dynamic effects relevant for turbine design conditions. For example, the development of low-level jets in nocturnal conditions can lead to high wind resources but under large wind speed and direction shear across the rotor. These and many other phenomena have been traditionally studied by boundary-layer meteorologist. In the wind energy context, the main objective is to understand the relevance of these weather phenomena in the predictive capacity of wind engineering design tools.

1.3. The Ambidextrous Validation Process.

Combining validation on flow cases with integrated case studies is the objective of the ambidextrous validation process summarized in Figure 3. The challenge is reviewed by the scientific community to define the modeling approach and expected capabilities in the form of the NEWA model-chain concept statement [11] and associated validation strategy [1]. The latter identifies the relevant phenomena that should be incorporated and suitable flow cases to validate model implementations addressing these phenomena. For example, the GABLS3 benchmark [12] was used to demonstrate the validity of the “tendencies” approach for meso-micro asynchronous coupling, using general mean flow and turbulence quantities and others specific to wind energy like the rotor-equivalent wind speed (*REWS*), the wind shear, etc. This feature is then tested within wind resource assessment methodologies to quantify the impact in terms of end-user integrated quantities of interest like annual energy prediction (*AEP*) and its associated uncertainty defined, for instance, in terms of the P_{90}/P_{50} percentile ratio of the estimated probabilistic distribution of *AEP* [13].

Figure 3: The ambidextrous validation process. (From [7], adapted to the NEWA context).

While the validation strategy for flow models considers a limited number of experiments and flow cases on the right side of the ambidextrous process, targeting specific

phenomena of interest, the assessment of the performance of design tools should reconsider a wide range of sites in all kinds of wind climate conditions. This is eventually achieved by incorporating operational data from industry on the left-side of the validation process. This allows applying probabilistic methods to infer uncertainties in the assessment of wind conditions based on the pool of validation data. The larger the data pool, the more confidence in the predictive capacity and expected uncertainties of the tools.

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2. Rödeser Berg Blind Test on the Modeling of a Forested Hill

2.1. Background: The Rödeser Berg Experiment

Site Description

This field campaign provides a unique dataset of wind measurements for validating models for flow over forested hilly terrain. The experiment was conducted on the Rödeser Berg, a hill (380m height) near Kassel, Germany (Figure 4). In October 2016, a three month intensive campaign relying heavily on remote sensing devices, i.e. lidar and sodar wind measurement systems, marked the beginning of the experiment. At the same time a one year long-term campaign using two tall masts started.

Figure 4: Location of the Rödeser Berg site in central Germany.

Fraunhofer IWES has conducted the measurement campaign in corporation with DTU Wind Energy. Furthermore ForWind, Enercon, innogy and Plankon/Innovent have provided wind measurement equipment for the Forested Hill Experiment Kassel.

The Rödeser Berg site is located in the federal state Hesse (Germany), around 20km northwest of the city of Kassel. The terrain height is between 200 m and 400m (hill top) (Figure 5 – left). The hill site is characterized by broadleaf forests with some spots of coniferous wood. Tree heights are around 20-35 m (Figure 5 – right). The roughness length in the area is in the range of 0.03 to 0.75 m (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Topography of the site (left) as well as forest heights in the same area (right). The red dot marks the position of the 200m met mast on top of the Rödeser Berg. Data Source (ALS data): Hessische Verwaltung für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation]

Figure 6: Roughness length distribution [based on CORINE-Dataset – EEA (2016)], converted to roughness lengths with the method by Silva, et. al 2007.

In Spring of 2015 a wind farm, consisting of four Enercon E 101 (3MW, rotor diameter: 101m, hub height 35m) became operational at the site. These turbines are located northwest of the 200m met mast on the hill-top.

Instrumentation

One of the tallest met masts in Germany; a 200 m Met mast is operated by Fraunhofer IWES on the top of the hill since 2011 (Callies et al. (2017)). This met mast is equipped with cup and sonic anemometers at various heights. Besides these temperature and a temperature difference sensor enable the measurement of atmospheric stability in terms of the Obukhov length at the hill top.

For the experiments conducted within NEWA, a second 140m met mast was erected for one year along the prevailing wind direction axis in the inflow to the hill. This met mast was well equipped with sonic and cup anemometers in vertical distances of at least 20m.

Measurement Campaign

Within the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) project an intense measurement campaign took place from October 2016 until January 2017 at the site. In total 17 measurement systems have been used: 9 lidar scanners, 5 lidar/sodar profilers and the 2 tall met masts.

Figure 7: Distribution of measurement devices during the intensive measurement campaign.

In addition to the met mast, three scanning and profiling lidars are of importance for the benchmarks. The positions of all for the benchmark relevant devices are marked in Figure 4. The UTM coordinates are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of measurement devices during the intensive measurement campaign.

Device	Type	UTMX [m] Zone 32 U	UTMY [m] Zone 32 U	Elevation [m]
MM200	Met Mast (hill top)	513590	5690182	388.0
MM140	Met Mast (southwest of hill)	511589	5687521	261.0
WS1 (Vara)	Wind Scanner (RHI at MM140)	511641	5687591	260.8
WS2 (#23)	Wind Scanner (RHI at MM200)	513589	5690178	392.8
WS6 (#58)	Wind Scanner (RHI at MM200)	513588	5690176	392.8
WP1	Wind Profiler	514804	5691869	254.6
WP3	Wind Profiler	512555	5688544	273.1
WP6	Wind Profiler	511642	5687589	260.8

Remarks

The prevailing wind direction at the site is south west. Consequently, the benchmarks will focus on the flow from this prevailing wind direction. For this wind direction none of the two met masts is influenced by the wakes of the wind turbines at the hill top. Thus, they do not need to be taken into account for this benchmark.

Figure 8: Terrain Height along the transect of 217 degrees (the red dots mark the positions of the met masts MM140, MM200 and the wind profiler WP1 (from left to right)).

The scan direction along the hill ridge is always 217 degrees. Figure 8 shows the terrain height as well as the position of the measurement devices along this transect. The benchmarks will ask for extraction of 2D-planes from the simulation along this axis. Please note: The wind direction might differ by some degrees from this. The cases to simulate for the benchmark represent typical inflow conditions.

Referencing

Please note: In case the terrain information (terrain height, terrain inclination, tree height, PAD) is used in any type of publication the provider of the data needs to be acknowledged as follows: Data Source (ALS data): Hessische Verwaltung für Bodenmanagement und Geoinformation]

References

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2.2. B01 - Flow over the Hill

Scope

The benchmark is a blind test starting in December 2017. Wind speed profiles on the hill top are provided, vertical (RHI) scans along the axis of 217° as well as profiler data and data from an additional mast are withheld for validation.

Data Accessibility

The benchmark is offered to participants of the NEWA (New European Wind Atlas) project and anyone else interested in participating.

Objectives

Evaluate flow across a forested hill. Evaluate turbulence models in a test site with well-defined boundary conditions. Evaluate also qualitatively the 2D flow across the forested hill.

Input data

The conditions for simulating the Kassel Forested Hill site are:

- Digitized map of the Rödeser Berg hill with a resolution of 10m.
- Digitized map of the Forest height on top of the hill with a resolution of 10m.
- Digitized Plant Area Density with a horizontal resolution of 10m and a vertical resolution of 1m.
- Digitized Roughness map derived from CORINE data [100m resolution]
- Wind Speeds/Directions: Measured at M200 (on the hill top) [30 min mean]
- Obukhov Length: Measured at 60 m at the 200m mast (on the hill top) [30 min mean]
- Coordinates of wind profilers along the transect line (217°)
- Gravity $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$, Coriolis parameter $f=1e-4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
- Use dry air with a density $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$.
- Mesoscale Tendencies will be provided at a later stage (after the Blind Test)

Validation data

The validation dataset is composed of mean flow and turbulence data from cup and sonic anemometers at two met masts and several lidar profilers along the main transect. All data are averaged over 30 min.

- Wind Speed Profiles at two met masts (one upstream, one on top of the hill)
- Wind Speed Profiles from 3 profiling lidars along the transect
- 2D field from RHI lidar scans along transect line (217°) through the M200 mast.

The validation dataset includes mean and standard deviation statistics from the ensemble profiles.

Model runs

The atmospheric conditions:

- Run 1 (Neutral Stratification – 17.11.2016 1120-1150 UTC): WD (MM200 at 188m) = 221.9°, WD (MM200 at 60m) = 219.7°, WS (MM200 at 188m) = 13.9 m/s, WS (MM200 at 60m) = 9.6 m/s, Obukhov length: ~4000m (MM200 at 60m)
- Run 2 (Slightly Stable Stratification – 18.11.2016 1600-1630 UTC): WD (MM200 at 188m) = 210.2°, WD (MM200 at 60m) = 196.5°, WS (MM200 at 188m) = 13.2 m/s, WS (MM200 at 60m) = 7.2 m/s, Obukhov length: ~350m (MM200 at 60m)
- Run 3 (Stable Stratification – 09.12.2016 0400-0430 UTC): WD (MM200 at 188m) = 248.2°, WD (MM200 at 60m) = 194.5°, WS (MM200 at 188m) = 11.5 m/s, WS (MM200 at 60m) = 8.2 m/s, Obukhov length: ~250m (MM200 at 60m)

or by best fit to the measured inlet profiles (at MM200) if the participant considers that this can improve the results. The computational domain must extend at least to $X = \pm 4000$ m in order to include the profilers upstream and downstream of the hill top and make sure that the hill wake is completely covered. The origin of the coordinate system should be placed at MM200 position [UTMX=513590, UTM Y=5690182, Zone: 32U] with X pointing East, Y pointing North and Z pointing up.

Output data

The simulated validation profiles consist on vertical profiles at mast and profiler positions of velocity components (U, V, W) and turbulence kinetic energy (tke). In addition, a two-dimensional field along the 217° transect crossing the location of the 200m met mast (MM200) should be provided.

The profiles should have the following order: X(m), Y(m), Z(m), U(m/s), V(m/s), W(m/s), tke(m²/s²). Use the file naming and format convention described in the Windbench user's guide with profID = prof#, where # = [MM140, MM200, WP1, WP3, WP6], i.e. 5 output files per user and model run. Please provide profile data from bottom to top of the modelled domain.

Additionally, please provide the 2D fields (streamwise-vertical) field that is centred around the 200m mast, along the 217° transect, i.e. negative values indicate values towards the southwest, positive values towards the northeast and thus the wake of the hill. This field must be exactly along 217°, independent of the exact inflow wind direction.

Please provide the field as ASCII-file with the following order: Dist(m), Z(m), U(m/s), V(m/s), W(m/s), tke(m²/s²), where Dist is the distance from MM200 and Z(m) and Z is the height above terrain, or as a in a netCDF file. Please provide the field up to a height of at least 800m above terrain.

An example file for the submission of the results can be found here: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/7SryqUb0nrRfcv3>

Please upload your data compressed in the following shared folder:
<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/cW934bziCPpwKUH>

(only upload is allowed, your data is only shared with the benchmark manager)

Remarks

There are no guidelines on the definition of the computational mesh and also on how to model the forests. Please describe in detail if and how you have modelled the forest. Please also comment on how you integrate grid dependency in the evaluation process. You can find other background documentation [here](#).

All input data is stored in the following shared (B2Drop) folder: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/NPXIOrxWL6fHd0A>

2.3. B02 - 2D Fields (Half-Blind)

Scope

The benchmark is a blind test starting in December 2017. A wind speed profile on the hill top is provided, in addition, a vertical (RHI) scan along the axis of 217° in the inflow to the hill top is given. Profiler data and additional met mast data as well as the vertical scan in the wake of the hill is withheld for validation

Data Accessibility

The benchmark is offered to participants of the NEWA (New European Wind Atlas) project and anyone else interested in participating.

Objectives

Evaluate flow across a forested hill. Evaluate turbulence models in a test site with well-defined boundary conditions. Evaluate the impact of model tuning.

Input data

The conditions for simulating the Kassel Forested Hill site are:

- Digitized map of the Rödeser Berg hill with a 10m resolution.
- Digitized map of the Forest height on top of the hill with 10m resolution.
- Digitized Plant Area Density with a horizontal resolution of 10m and a vertical resolution of 1m.
- Digitized Roughness map derived from CORINE data [100m resolution]
- Wind Speeds/Directions: Measured at M200 (on the hill top) [30 min mean]
- Obukhov Length: Measured at 60 m at the 200m mast (on the hill top) [30 min mean]
- Coordinates of wind profilers/met masts along the transect line (217°)
- Gravity $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$, Coriolis parameter $f=1e-4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
- Use dry air with a density $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$.
- Image from an RHI lidar scan (vertical plane) along the transect line (217°) from the inflow up to the hill-top

Validation data

The validation dataset is composed of mean flow and turbulence data from cup and sonic anemometers, lidar profilers and lidar scanners. All data are averaged over 30 min.

The following data will be used for evaluation:

- Wind Speed Profiles at the two met masts
- Wind Speed Profiles from 3 Profilers along the Transect
- 2D field from RHI lidar scans along transect line (217°) through the M200 mast.

The validation dataset includes mean and standard deviation statistics from the ensemble profiles

Model runs

The atmospheric conditions:

- Run 1 (Neutral Stratification – 18.11.2016 22:20-22:50UTC): WD (MM200 at 188m)= 223.7° , WS (MM200 at 188m) = 16.9 m/s, WS (MM200 at 60m) = 10.9 m/s, Obukhov length: ~5000m (MM200 at 60m)

or by best fit to the measured inlet profiles (at MM200) if the participant considers that this can improve the results. The computational domain must extend at least to $X = \pm 4000$ m in order to include the profilers upstream and downstream of the hill top and make sure that the hill wake is completely covered. The origin of the coordinate system should be placed at MM200 position [UTMX=513590, UTM Y=5690182, Zone: 32U] with X pointing East, Y pointing North and Z pointing up.

Output data

The simulated validation profiles consist on vertical profiles at mast and profiler positions of velocity components (U,V,W) and turbulence kinetic energy (tke). In addition, a two-dimensional field along the 217° transect crossing the location of the 200m met mast (MM200) should be provided.

The profiles should have the following order: X(m), Y(m), Z(m), U(m/s), V(m/s), W(m/s), tke(m^2/s^2). Use the file naming and format convention described in the Windbench user's guide with profID = prof#, where # = [MM140, MM200, WP1, WP3, WP6], i.e. 5 output files per user and model run. Please provide profile data from bottom to top of the modelled domain.

Additionally, please provide the 2D fields (streamwise-vertical) field that is centred around the 200m mast, along the 217° transect, i.e. negative values indicate values towards the southwest, positive values towards the northeast and thus the wake of the hill. This field must be exactly along 217° , independent of the exact inflow wind direction.

Please provide the field as ASCII-file with the following order: Dist(m), Z(m), U(m/s), V(m/s), W(m/s), tke(m^2/s^2), where Dist is the distance from MM200 and Z(m) and Z is the height above terrain, or as a in a netCDF file. Please provide the field up to a height of at least 800m above terrain.

An example file for the submission of the results can be found here:
<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/7SryqUb0nrRfcv3>

Please upload your data compressed in the following shared folder: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/oRPwdwwiQ9Naw5d>

(only upload is allowed, your data is only shared with the benchmark manager)

Remarks

In order to evaluate the added value of model fine-tuning it is important that you describe how this is performed. Please report on the deviations with respect to default settings (e.g. those of the Kassel Benchmark I – Half-Blind or how you usually would set-up your simulations without knowing the field). There are no guidelines on the definition of the computational mesh and also on how to model the forests. Please describe in detail if and how you have modelled the forest. Please also comment on how you integrate grid dependency in the evaluation process. You can find the input and validation files as well as other background documentation [here](#)

All input data is stored in the following shared (B2Drop) folder: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/UB498d5gMcU7sSO>

3. Hornamossen: Flow over Undulated Forested Terrain

3.1. Background: The Hornamossen Experiment

Site Description

The location of the site can be seen in Figure 9, where the red box indicates the area of Figure 10 and Figure 11 which shows the elevation and tree height deduced from airborne laser scans. Figure 12 and Figure 13 shows the same thing but in larger zoom. The forest consists predominately of spruce, but is mixed with pine and some deciduous forest types. The site includes a variety of heterogeneities in both topography and land cover. The forest itself is also heterogeneous with patches of trees of different densities, height and age. The site is typical for wind energy exploration in Sweden and offers many possibilities of investigating heterogeneities in the wind field due to vegetation and elevation.

Instrumentation

Tower measurements

The tower was 180 m high, square, with 1.2 m wide sides. It was equipped with 8 Metek 3D ultra sonics, 7 Thies first class anemometers, 3 Vaisala anemometers, 3 wind vanes, and a temperature profile system. The majority of the instrumentation in the tower was financed by the ForestWind project, apart from the cups and vanes which was financed by OX2 Vindkompaniet. Additional instruments, such as two Kipp & Zonen 4-way radiation sensors at 30 and 0.5 m have been placed at the location of tower as part of the NEWA campaign. The tower instruments were operational between June 2015 and July 2017.

Remote sensing instruments

The location of the remote sensing instruments is best seen in Figure 12 where they are indicated by their model name. At the tower site there was a Zephir 300 lidar measuring at the same heights as the tower, but recording raw data in order to validate the lidar performance and provide redundancy to the tower measurements. An additional Zephir 300 was deployed at the most western location, measuring the wind speed up to 300 m and also recording raw data. Most of the validation points consist of AQ systems AQ510 sodar profilers. They measure the wind profile between 40 and 200 m with 5 m resolution. RAW data was recorded to enable additional analysis on turbulence and boundary layer height. The sodars were all validated at the 180 m tower or another 100 m tower at a nearby site before deployment.

One of the remote sensing points was equipped with a Leosphere V1 lidar (40-200 m), a Leosphere WLS70 lidar (100-1500 m) and a Vaisala ceilometer backscatter lidar, with the aim of covering the wind profile in the whole boundary layer, and using the ceilometer backscatter information to monitor the boundary layer height. The two Leosphere lidars suffered from different mechanical problems, mainly with the wiper and

the cooling which caused low signal to noise ratio. The problems also caused low availability. In order to increase the availability, new statistics were calculated from the radial velocities from each pulse, fitting Gaussian distributions to the radial velocities and calculating the mean wind speed from the center of the Gaussian distributions.

The remote sensing campaign ran between April and October 2016, but some of the instruments were removed in August.

A figure showing the wind profile from the tower and the remote sensing profilers can be seen in Figure 6, and based on the overlap of the 95 % confidence intervals the instruments are considered to measure the same wind speed.

Pressure gradient measurements

An earlier Benchmark study over forests (Ivanell et al 2018) highlighted the problem for modelers of adjusting the pressure gradient or geostrophic wind in order to match a target wind speed at some height. In an attempt to remove that complication by measuring the static pressure gradient a system of four DigiQuartz 6000-16B-IS microbarometers was deployed in a square with around 3 km sides. To minimize the bluff-body and dynamic-pressure effects the sensors were placed in wind shielded locations beneath the canopy. Comparisons of the calculated geostrophic wind speed to the wind speed above the boundary layer as measured by the profilers showed that the pressure gradient system was able to measure the static pressure, but noise in the data require a sufficient averaging time to be used.

Remarks

The Hornamossen site was equipped with flow model validation in mind. Much of the motivation for the experiment design comes from an earlier experiment with a 140 tall tower over a similar forest, but with much less topographical complexity preceded this experiment. The main results from that experiment can be seen in Bergström et al 2013 and Arnqvist et al 2015. One conclusion was that the boundary layer height is a promising scaling factor for many of the characteristics of the wind important for wind energy i.e. wind turning, wind shear, and profiles of second and third order moments. That was the basis of recording raw data from the sodars as well as including the long range profiler and the ceilometer. Another conclusion from Arnqvist et al 2015 was that effects of stratification becomes very prominent on higher heights and was seen to effect almost all statistical moments as well as the roughness length which was shown to decrease in stable stratification. With that in mind, the benchmarks coming out of the Hornamossen experiment will focus on a variety of stratifications as well as transitions between different stratifications.

Figure 9: A map of Sweden with the measurement region highlighted.

Figure 10: Elevation map. The color scaling shows the height above sea level. The red crosses marks the positions of the instruments used in the campaign.

Figure 11: Tree height map.. The color scaling shows the tree height as derived by airborne laser scans. The red crosses marks the positions of the instruments used in the campaign.

Figure 12: Zoom-in of Figure 10.

Figure 13: Zoom in of Figure 11.

3.2. Hornamossen Diurnal Cycle

Scope

The benchmark is open to anyone interested in participating, but is specifically aimed at studying models for potential use in the making of the NEWA.

Objectives

The task is to model the flow in complex forested terrain and provide wind-profile estimates at a number of validation locations. The motivation is to study how well models can capture the differences in wind profiles in different locations of a typical wind farm, during different atmospheric conditions. Hence, the objective is very similar to the objective of a normal wind resource siting process.

There are two cases, one with easterly and one with westerly flow. Both cases cover diurnal cycles in relatively clear sky conditions and hence include both stable, unstable and neutral atmospheric stratification as well as transitions between different conditions. Validation is made both on the diurnal average as well as in different stratifications. The cases has been selected based on the criteria of stationary geostrophic wind speed and direction in order to simplify the modeling process as well as barotropic conditions in order to simplify the evaluation of model performance.

The feat of modelling a full diurnal cycle is challenging, so the benchmark will also accept submissions that are only modelled in stationary conditions, neutrally stratified or otherwise.

Data accessibility

The benchmark is open to anyone willing to participate. The results of the benchmark will be compiled into a scientific paper in which the models will be shown by their name.

Input data

The surface data consists of a data set with 10x10 m resolution covering 40x40 km and containing elevation height, forest height and Plant Area Density (PAD) provided in netCDF format. The vertical resolution of PAD is 1 m. The vertically integrated PAD, the PAI is also included for simplicity. A flag for water surface is also included, with the value 1 for water and 0 otherwise.

Input data for the boundary conditions of the models is provided in netCDF format and comes from a 3x3 km resolution run by the mesoscale model WRF, these include wind speed, heat fluxes, temperatures, tendencies, geostrophic wind speed and boundary layer height for 72 hours. Since the validation cases are relatively stationary, it is sufficient to provide output data during 24 h.

Furthermore the coordinates of the validation points are provided:

Table 2: Coordinates of the validation points.

Site	N (decimal)	E (decimal)	N (sweref99TM)	E (sweref99TM)
Lidar 1	57,983524°	13,852550°	6427452	432146
Sodar 1	57,980028°	13,869437°	6427046	433138
Sodar 2	57,979254°	13,887554°	6426942	434208
Sodar 3	57,982832°	13,899281°	6427329	434908
Lidar 2	57,979228°	13,910451°	6426917	435562
Sodar 4	57,983893°	13,938416°	6427410	437224
Sodar 5	57,985541°	13,951965°	6427581	438028
Sodar 6	57,991304°	13,962402°	6428213	438655
Sodar 7	57,995487°	14,022150°	6428626	442194
Tower	57,980767°	13,941654°	6427059	437410

And in SWEREF99TM:

The coordinate system of the input data is in SWEREF99TM, which is a coordinate format with longitude, latitude and latitude measured as distance in meter from a reference point.

Validation data

Velocity and TKE values will be normalized with respect to the tower measurement at 100 m. The validation dataset includes measurements during four full diurnal cycles in each case. The use of validation measurements from several diurnal cycles enables estimation of the confidence of the measurements as well as it provides some redundancy for instrument down time.

Model runs

There are two cases. Winds coming from the east, and winds coming from the west. Both runs should cover time series from at least one full diurnal cycle. If that is not possible to calculate, stationary runs are also interesting, such as a weighted average between runs in different atmospheric stratifications or, in the simplest case, one stationary run for a single atmospheric state. In that case, suitable geostrophic wind speeds and directions are 12.2 m/s, 115° (east case) and 11.7 m/s, 264° (west case)

Following the conclusions of Ivanell et al (2018) the following constant values should be used when using the Sogachev et al (2012) turbulence model:

$$\kappa = 0.4, C_d = 0.2, C_{\varepsilon 1} = 1.176, C_{\varepsilon 2} = 1.920, \sigma_\kappa = 1, \sigma_\varepsilon = 1.238 \text{ and } C_\mu = 0.033$$

Output data

Output quantities and dimensions:

- dimensions: time (t), position (x,y,z)

- time-height: U, V velocity components, , where U is the east-west component, positive eastward, V is the south-north component, positive northwards, turbulent kinetic energy (TKE), and if possible potential temperature (Th).
- Planes at 100,150 and 200 m above local ground height of wind components U and V, as well as TKE. These planes should cover as many of the validation points as possible, which in most cases is expected to be more or less the size of the inner modelling domain. The planes should contain one hour block averages starting and ending with the regular clock hours.

If other boundary conditions are used than the ones provided by the input, please also provide these.

To homogenize the output data please consider these indications:

- time series should be provided based on 10-min or 1-hr block averages
- Vertical profiles should be provided in the whole boundary layer.
- Please follow the same format as the input .nc file
- Naming convention for variables can be find at <http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/50/build/cf-standard-name-table.html> and also in the input files.

Remarks

The east case starts at 15:00 local time, whereas the west case starts 00:00 local time. Both cases does however include input data for 72 hours. The meso scale model results has been compared to the measurements of the campaign to ensure that they agree to such an extent that permits validation of the model results by the measurements. The reason why measurements is not directly given as input data is the desire to test the entire NEWA modelling chain. As long as the wind directions, wind speeds, and fluxes agree reasonably between the measurements and the meso scale model, the differences by using either as input data has been deemed minor.

3.3. References

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4. NEWA Meso-Micro Challenge for Wind Resource Assessment

4.1. Background

This challenge is organized in the context of the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) project, whose overarching goal is to produce a seamless high resolution wind atlas for Europe. The wind atlas methodology will be based on a mesoscale to microscale (meso-micro) model-chain, validated with dedicated experiments as well as other observational databases from public and private sources. Wind resource assessment is related to the development of wind farms and implies the prediction of long-term wind statistics, notably the annual energy prediction (AEP).

In the development of meso-micro methodologies for wind resource assessment there is a tradeoff to be made between modeling fidelity and its associated cost to yield the required accuracy for the intended use (Figure 14). Accuracy is a qualitative concept that is used here to define the closeness of agreement between the predicted quantity of interest and the true value in the real world. Considering wind resource assessment applications, accuracy should gradually improve from the early-stage prospecting phase to the project financing phase, i.e. from planning to bankable accuracy. This process will hopefully remove the bias and reduce the uncertainty of the assessment to desired financial limits. This typically implies using off-the-shelf wind atlas products during early planning phase to design tools of increasing fidelity as the project matures. The required fidelity will depend on the complexity of the site as indicated in Figure 1 and is capped by the maximum allocated cost in terms of computing time.

Figure 14: Illustration of the process of improved accuracy ΔU from planning to bankable thresholds against the maximum allocated computing time cost for different site/flow complexities.

Hierarchy of Meso-Micro Methodologies

A hierarchy of meso-micro methodologies for wind resource assessment is illustrated in Figure 15, ranging from the Global Wind Atlas lower-end of modeling fidelity, where the WAsP downscaling method is used directly from global reanalysis data without

mesoscale modeling, to the dynamic coupling of a mesoscale model with a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model based on large-eddy simulation (LES) in the higher-end of modeling fidelity. The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) mesoscale model will be used in NEWA to produce the wind atlas and, therefore, it is explicitly mentioned in Figure 1, also as the most popular choice for a mesoscale model. Between these limits, a hierarchy of methodologies is established depending on the type of coupling and the type of CFD model. Since the application demands statistical quantities of interest, we shall leave dynamical coupling methods out of the design tools range. In the context of NEWA, wind farm design tools will be based on statistical downscaling methodologies that combine WRF outputs with steady or unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) microscale CFD model simulations that include thermal stratification.

Similarly, uncertainty quantification can also have different levels of fidelity depending on how rigorous is the analysis; from ad-hoc engineering methods to formal UQ probabilistic methods.

Figure 15: Hierarchy of meso-micro methodologies for wind resource assessment classified in terms of the type of coupling and typical intended use.

Objectives

The objectives of this challenge are:

- To determine the applicability range of meso-micro methodologies for wind resource assessment within the NEWA validation domain.
- To establish open-access practices for the assessment of these methodologies to improve the traceability of the state-of-the-art as additional datasets are incorporated in the validation domain.
- To identify knowledge-gaps that will feed plans for future targeted experiments and validation activities.
- To engage with lead users of the NEWA model-chain whose first release will be provided open-access in June 2018.

Validation Data

The ultimate goal is to incorporate as many sites as possible in the challenge, at least during the duration of the NEWA project (until April 2019). This will constitute the "NEWA validation domain" as illustrated in Figure 16, overlapping with the application domain.

Figure 16: Illustration of the NEWA validation domain overlapping with the wind energy application domain, both mapped in terms of the range of operating conditions versus the flow complexity to be modeled.

The intended validation domain spans modeling conditions supported by high-quality data, for which the methodologies are well understood, such that there is good agreement between observations and simulations.

The application range not covered by NEWA shall be filled with future experiments and industry data. By supporting an open-access database and assessment process it will be possible to sustain a more traceable development of wind resource assessment technology.

4.2. Phase 1: Cabauw and Fino1

Status

The first results of this benchmark for the Cabauw site have been published in the Torque 2018 conference, 20-22 Jun 2018:

- Benchmark data: <https://b2share.eudat.eu/records/87904b9740cf4defaca8a16070670ead>
- Evaluation script: <https://github.com/windbench/NEWAMesoMicroChallengePhase1>
- Conference paper: Sanz Rodrigo J, Chávez Arroyo R, Gancarski P, Borbón Guillén F, Avila M, Garcons J, Folch A, Cavar D, Allaerts D, Meyers J, Dutrieux A (2018) Comparing Meso-Micro Methodologies for Annual Wind Resource Assessment and Turbine Siting at Cabauw. *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.*, 1037: 072030, <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1037/7/072030/meta>

Scope

This first phase will be the basis to establish an assessment process for meso-micro wind resource assessment methodologies. To this end, initial datasets from two sites in horizontally homogeneous conditions are proposed:

- Cabauw, onshore, and
- Fino1 offshore

such that single-column models can be used cost-effectively as proxy for 3D RANS models. This will provide a more efficient approach to test statistical methodologies that can be later applied to heterogeneous sites in 3D.

Data Accessibility

Data from Cabauw and Fino1 are provided here reformatted to a common standard based on the original data from, respectively, KNMI's CESAR¹ and BSH's FINO² official web repositories.

Objectives

The objectives of the challenge apply in this first phase as follows:

- Test meso-micro methodologies consistently for two sites and map accuracy vs cost for relevant quantities of interest, notably for annual energy production (AEP) and site suitability parameters.
- Establish open-access practices for the assessment of these methodologies that can determine the added value of meso-micro with respect to conventional methods based on microscale modeling only.
- Compare methodologies for uncertainty estimation of gross AEP and discuss their adequacy to the wind resource assessment process used by industry.

Input data

Input data is stored in the following shared folder: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/AkmYTfRd2l6kROo>

Observations

One year of observations from two tall masts are provided in NetCDF format:

- Cabauw: 200-m mast, year 2006 (51.971°N, 4.927°E)
- Fino-1: 100-m mast, year 2006 (54.0143°N, 6.5933°E)

Elevation and Land Cover

Microscale models shall consider a uniform roughness length for Cabauw of 0.15 m, as in the GABLS3 benchmark. For Fino-1, surface roughness shall depend on wind conditions through the Charnock relation, $z_0 = C_{ch}u^2/g$, with $C_{ch} = 0.0062$, calibrated in neutral conditions for year 2006 in [1].

Mesoscale Forcing

You are welcome to use your own mesoscale simulations to feed the meso-micro methodology. However, if you only plan to run microscale simulations, for consistency you should use the mesoscale input forcing provided herein.

Mesoscale input forcing in terms of mesoscale tendencies is provided for the sites following the same methodology of the GABSL3 benchmark case and described in [2]. For each site, a reference WRF configuration based on one-way telescoping nests at 27,

¹ <http://www.cesar-observatory.nl/>

² http://www.bsh.de/en/Marine_data/Projects/FINO/index.jsp

9 and 3 km horizontal resolution, all of them with grid dimensions of 61x61 and 61 vertical levels up to 5000 Pa. The yearly period is integrated based on two-day runs with an additional day for spin-up. Simulations are initialized at 12UTC using ERA-Interim reanalysis data. The U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) land-use surface data, that comes by default with the WRF model, is used together with the unified Noah land-surface model to define the boundary conditions at the surface. Other physical parameterizations used are: the rapid radiative transfer model (RRTM), the Dudhia radiation scheme and the Yonsei University (YSU) first-order PBL scheme.

A NetCDF file for mesoscale data is provided with the following information:

- Site coordinates and Coriolis parameter
- Time-height 2D arrays of velocity components (U, V, W) and potential temperature (Th)
- Time-height 2D arrays of mesoscale forcings (tendencies): geostrophic wind (Ug, Vg), advective wind ($Uadv, Vadv$) and advective potential temperature ($Thadv$)
- Time array of surface-layer quantities: friction velocity (ust), kinematic heat flux (wt), 2-m temperature ($T2$), skin temperature (TSK), surface pressure ($Psfc$)

Units, dimensions and variables description are all provided in the NetCDF file. Momentum tendencies are provided in [$m\ s^{-1}$] and should be multiplied by the Coriolis parameter ($f_c = 0.00115\ s^{-1}$) to obtain appropriate forces in [$m\ s^{-2}$]. For convenience, we have omitted information about humidity since the assumption of dry-atmosphere is typically adopted by wind energy flow models.

Reference Power Curve

The NREL 5 MW reference power curve will be used to evaluate AEP [3]. A text file is provided with other additional wind speed relationships computed by NREL.

Validation data

The following quantities of interest will be evaluated at the three sites:

- Horizontal wind speed (S) and direction (WD) distributions at a reference hub-height of 80 m
- AEP_{gross} ($p50, p90$) at 80 m using the NREL 5MW reference power curve
- Velocity and turbulence intensity profiles for 16 wind direction sectors and three stability classes

Stability will be characterized based on the local Obukhov length L using the stability parameter z/L , where L is obtained from sonic anemometer measurements at 3 m in Cabauw and at 40 m in Fino-1. Stability classes are defined as follows:

- Unstable (u): $-20 < z/L < -0.2$
- Weakly unstable (wu): $-0.2 < z/L < -0.02$
- Neutral (n): $-0.02 < z/L < 0.02$
- Weakly stable (ws): $0.02 < z/L < 0.2$
- Stable (s): $0.2 < z/L < 20$

Model runs

Consistent with the philosophy of the challenge, each participant should develop a plan to span the accuracy vs cost figure. For instance:

- A WRF modeler could run yearly simulations starting from the 3-nest configuration of the reference set-up (or a different one) and add other 3 nests switching to LES down to resolutions of the order of 100 m and provide 6 results, one from each nest, for the 3 sites.
- A CFD modeler may vary the number of simulations included in the assessment and/or decide to increase resolution or switch to a higher-fidelity turbulence model when switching from planning to design phase.

For each *AEP* assessment you should provide the cost in cpu-hr.

Also adopting the end-user perspective, the simulations may consider how to best use the onsite measurements to calibrate their model-chain to the reference mast. This is equivalent to a conventional micrositing process in the design phase of ensuring that self-prediction at the *reference* site is free of bias before extrapolating horizontally or vertically to other target *prediction* sites. Introducing calibration is clear way of distinguishing between planning and design phase in the accuracy vs cost figure although the cpu-time may be roughly the same.

For consistency with the GABLS3 benchmark, microscale models using Sogachev et al. (2012) k - ϵ turbulence model shall use this set of constants: $\kappa = 0.4$, $C_{\epsilon 1} = 1.52$, $C_{\epsilon 2} = 1.833$, $\sigma_k = 2.95$, $\sigma_{\epsilon} = 2.95$ and $C_{\mu} = 0.03$ [4].

Output data

Data should be provided in a single NetCDF file per site, as described in the python template based on the reference WRF simulation. Following the example above, the WRF-LES approach should provide $6 \times 2 = 12$ files.

Output quantities and dimensions:

- dimensions: time (t), height above ground (z), zflux height of surface-layer quantities
- time-height: U, V velocity components, potential temperature (Th), turbulent kinetic energy (TKE)
- time: friction velocity (u_s), kinematic heat flux (wt) and/or Obukhov length (L) at zflux height and 2-m temperature (T2)

To homogenize the output data please consider these indications:

- time series should be provided based on 10-min or 1-hr averages
- Vertical profiles should be provided at the simulation levels.
- A python script is provided to help you figure out the output format. Please respect the naming convention for variables to allow automatic post-processing.
- Time series: please follow the same format as the input .nc file, mean profiles will be generated in the post-processing.

- Mean profiles: format to be defined soon, will be added to the python script

Please upload your data compressed in the following shared folder:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/OPk7P8l4kUgD7b7> (only upload is allowed, your data is only shared with the benchmark manager)

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4.3. Activities so far and Learning Outcomes

Initial results of Phase 1 were published in the Torque 2018 conference.

<http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1037/7/072030/meta>

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